

Grant Agreement number: 101095017

Project acronym: COOPERATE

Project coordinator: TU/e

Project title: COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

Deliverable D3.1 – Platform and compliance criteria – Release I

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN

CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE

STAM

BRAINPORT DEVELOPMENT NV

SCIENCE CITY LYNGBY

DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET

IDEA STRATEGISCHE ECONOMISCHE CONSULTING

WP3 – Set-up and Develop the Network of ERA Hubs

WP leader – IDEA

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

PROJECT TITLE

COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards Era-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

Project Number	101095017
Project Acronym	COOPERATE
GA Number	101095017
Project Coordinator	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN (TU/e)
Project Duration	30 months
Deliverable Number	D3.1
Deliverable Title	Platform and compliance criteria – Release I
Deliverable Description	Platform and compliance criteria – Release I
Dissemination Level	PU-Public
Work Package Number	WP3
Lead Beneficiary	IDEA
Deliverable Due Date	31/12/2023
Submission Date	23/12/2023
Submission Version	V2.0

Table of Contents

<i>Executive Summary</i>	3
<i>List of abbreviation/Nomenclature</i>	4
<i>Table of figures and tables</i>	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Context and framework	6
2.1 Defining the components of an ERA Hub	7
2.2 Assessing the maturity levels	8
2.3 Measuring maturity levels	9
2.4 Labelling or scoring system to measure the degree of maturity of ecosystems	12
3 Compliance criteria	12
3.1 Research	13
3.2 Talent.....	14
3.3 Knowledge transfer	15
3.4 Funding	16
3.5 Collaboration.....	17
3.6 Governance	18
3.7 Innovation.....	19
4 Guidelines & recommendations	20
4.1 Research	20
4.2 Talent.....	21
4.3 Knowledge transfer	21
4.4 Funding	22
4.5 Collaboration.....	23
4.6 Governance	24
4.7 Innovation.....	24
5 Next steps	25

Executive Summary

This document, titled "D3.1 – Platform & Compliance Criteria - Release I" serves as a comprehensive guide outlining the platform and compliance criteria which are at the core of the project to integrate the Toolbox and Playbook developed within Work Package (WP) 2 and manage the ecosystems journey to create a network of ERA Hubs

This report corresponds to the efforts conducted within Work Package 3, Task 3.1, where IDEA Consult takes the lead, under the overall leadership of STAM as WP 3 leader. The overarching objective of this WP is to develop the platform and compliance criteria essential for setting up and advancing the ERA Hubs network. It aims to attract and connect stakeholders from EU ecosystems, including policy makers and society at large, while promoting the utilisation of the Toolbox and Playbook through online digital tools.

The report begins by providing a contextual overview of the COOPERATE project and the ERA Hub framework, which is structured as a 4D matrix encompassing mission, thematic scope, lines of action, and actors involved. Additionally, the report summarizes various approaches identified for measuring and assessing ecosystems maturity levels, a critical factor in gauging their progress toward becoming ERA Hubs.

Aligned with the above-mentioned framework, the report introduces compliance criteria, grounded in the identified lines of action for ERA Hubs, as detailed in the Playbook. Finally, the document outlines a set of guidelines to assess the compliance criteria, determining how well an ecosystem aligns with the proposed ERA hubs model. These guidelines, akin to the compliance criteria, are crafted based on the identified lines of action.

This document has been written by IDEA Consult and approved by Technische Universiteit Eindhoven (TU/e).

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
ERA	European Research Area
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
LERL	Local Ecosystem Readiness Level
R&I	Research and Innovation
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Table of figures and tables

Figure 1: Framework for the COOPERATE project.....	7
Figure 2: Initial ERA Hub model	8
Figure 3: Degree of networking towards collaboration	10
Figure 4: Local Ecosystem Readiness Level classification.....	11
Figure 5: Phase of ERA Hub development	11
Table 1 Compliance criteria related to the research line of action for a future ERA Hub	13
Table 2 Compliance criteria related to the talent line of action for a future ERA Hub.....	14
Table 3 Compliance criteria related to the knowledge transfer line of action for a future ERA Hub	15
Table 4 Compliance criteria related to the funding line of action for a future ERA Hub	16
Table 5 Compliance criteria related to the collaboration line of action for a future ERA Hub	17
Table 6 Compliance criteria related to the governance line of action for a future ERA Hub.....	18
Table 7 Compliance criteria related to the innovation line of action for a future ERA Hub	19

1 Introduction

The following document is prepared in the context of the COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production (COOPERATE) project and aims to outline the platform and compliance criteria including:

- Recapping the context and framework
- Highlighting the compliance criteria
- Outlining initial guidelines

The details related to each of these points are outlined in the document below.

2 Context and framework

An ERA Hub should be envisioned as a **sustainable triple or quadruple helix place-based collaboration** of independent actors located in a specific geographical area and working through joint actions towards a common mission and contributing to the region's Smart Specialisation Strategy.

Within an ERA Hub, universities and knowledge and technology institutions play a key role and that facilitates knowledge transfer, exploitation, and commercialisation. ERA Hubs need to be dynamic and evolve over time to be able to adapt to a changing environment and can present various levels of maturity. A well-developed ERA Hub is expected to:

- 1) Promote the generation of high-quality **research** that can contribute to the global body of knowledge.
- 2) Help to develop and educate future **talent** pools by providing opportunities for learning, training, and development.
- 3) Facilitate **knowledge transfer** and the exchange of ideas by providing opportunities for networking, dissemination, and collaboration.
- 4) Help to ensure the availability, visibility and access to relevant **funding** options to support the growth and development of key sectors.
- 5) Promote **collaboration** by bringing together researchers, innovators, industry representatives, policymakers, and other stakeholders from different regions and sectors.
- 6) Develop an effective **governance** system for the creation of robust partnerships between the stakeholders of the quadruple helix, encompassing academia, industry, government, and civil society.
- 7) Help to drive ground-breaking **innovation** and the valorisation of ideas, leading to the development of new technologies, products, and services.

2.1 Defining the components of an ERA Hub

The high-level concept of the ERA Hub as conceived in the Grant Agreement (para. 1.2.1) is organised in the form of a 4D matrix comprising four main components, namely Mission, Thematic scope, Lines of action and Actors involved.

Figure 1: Framework for the COOPERATE project

Source: Consortium partners

Mission

The mission refers to the alignment of objectives of the triple/quadruple helix collaboration across actors within and between ecosystems. It determines the long-term approach and is based on a common understanding of the priorities for the local and regional ecosystem.

Thematic Scope

The thematic scope indicates the areas on which common action will be prioritised. This scope is determined by the mission and will in general contribute to the region's Smart Specialisation Strategies or value chains of importance to the ecosystem.

Lines of action

The ERA Hub Framework is built on seven lines of action: Research, Talent, Knowledge transfer, Funding, Collaboration, Governance, and Innovation. These lines of action refer to the joint activities carried out within the context of the ERA Hub. These lines of actions can contribute to the attraction and development of R&I talent in the ecosystem, to the development and opening of research and technology infrastructures, to the creation of new mechanisms of access to finance for entrepreneurs and start-ups, and to a strengthened engagement of citizens and other stakeholders in R&I activities.

Actors

Actors are a key component of an ERA Hub as they are the ones driving the activities and orientation of the ecosystem. The number and types of actors involved in triple/quadruple helix collaboration within an ERA Hub will depend on the characteristics of the ecosystem and the willingness to cooperate. Participation and active involvement in an ERA Hub should be voluntary and therefore good incentives and governance are key to sustain the participation and an active engagement of the actors. Based on preliminary work by the partners, an initial ERA Hub model has been conceived as starting point for the co-creation activities. The model builds on the lines of action (e.g., access to knowledge and talents) which gathers a set of initiatives/projects to animate the actors and stakeholders and operate the ecosystem around common priorities (i.e., strategic multi-annual roadmap) which reflects the mission-based approach, see Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Initial ERA Hub model

Source: Consortium partners

As a starting point, to be refined within WP1, the Consortium will be inspired by the Report from the Expert Group on Policy Indicators for Responsible Research and Innovation (Roger et al. 2015) to comply with the ERA Hub framework model and the 4D matrix representing the operational and governance layers along the Lines of Action 7, in which a dynamic framework for RRI indicators is recommended. This framework will be adapted to comply with the ERA Hub framework model and the 4D matrix representing the operational and governance layers along the Lines of Action.

2.2 Assessing the maturity levels

While the initial model depicted in Figure 5 defines the main components of an ERA Hub, the measurement and assessment of ecosystems play a crucial role in determining their progress towards

becoming ERA Hubs. The assessment of the maturity level of ecosystems can be analysed from two different angles:

- A first option is that the ecosystems are evaluated by external evaluators in a centralized manner. This approach has the advantage that the evaluation process is done homogeneously for all ecosystems interested in getting insights on the level of maturity of their ecosystem. This approach has, however, some drawbacks, most notably the fact that it would require the creation of a centralized secretariat in charge of the evaluation and assessment of ecosystems.
- The second option is that ecosystems themselves assess their level of maturity (e.g., through self-assessment tools included in the platform). In this case, the approach would be entire bottom-up, leaving more room for adaptation and interpretation, which might improve the degree to which the model is adaptable to diverse settings and contexts.

The upcoming cocreation sessions will analyse and discuss the pros and cons of these two approaches, prioritizing two main impact dimensions: sustainability (e.g., which approaches can better ensure the sustainability of the approach over time) and adaptability (e.g., which approach can better respond to the needs of diverse types of ecosystems). The discussions will also shed light on the best approach to select who will be in charge of evaluating the ecosystem: (e.g., an evaluation board in the case of having a centralized evaluation approach, the actors – or a group thereof – involved in the ecosystem in case the evaluation is done at the level of the ecosystems themselves).

2.3 Measuring maturity levels

An example of assessment is shown in Figure 3 by Russel & Smorodinskaya (2018), which illustrates the degrees of networking towards collaboration. The figure represents a continuum of networking stages, ranging from basic networking to advanced collaboration. At the basic networking stage, individuals or organizations establish connections and engage in information sharing without significant collaboration or joint activities. As networking progresses, it transitions to cooperative networking, where participants begin to collaborate on specific projects or initiatives while maintaining a certain degree of autonomy. Moving further along the continuum, the figure depicts coordinated networking, characterized by a higher level of collaboration and coordination among stakeholders, often involving joint planning and resource sharing. Finally, at the advanced collaboration stage, the highest degree of networking is reached, with deep and integrated collaboration, joint decision-making, and shared goals. The figure highlights the evolving nature of networking towards increased levels of collaboration, emphasizing the importance of progressing from basic connections to more advanced forms of collaborative engagement for achieving shared objectives and fostering innovation.

Figure 3: Degree of networking towards collaboration

Source: Russel & Smorodinskava, 2018

To apply this figure to ecosystem maturity assessment, evaluators can examine the extent to which the ecosystem demonstrates characteristics associated with each stage of networking. This assessment can be done through a combination of qualitative and quantitative measures.

- Qualitatively, evaluators can examine the depth and nature of relationships and interactions among ecosystem actors, looking for evidence of networking at each stage. This could involve analysing the level of information sharing, cooperation, coordination, and joint decision-making among stakeholders.
- Quantitative measures can complement the qualitative assessment by providing objective data points that indicate the ecosystem's level of collaboration and networking. This may include metrics such as the number and nature of collaborations or partnerships formed, joint projects initiated, shared resources and infrastructure utilized, and the overall impact of collaborative activities on innovation and ecosystem development.

By considering both qualitative and quantitative indicators aligned with the degrees of networking towards collaboration, evaluators can place an ecosystem into a specific level of maturity, similarly to the concept of local Ecosystem Readiness Level (ERL) as discussed by Sarri et al. 2020, where level 1 is the lowest, and it represents the total absence of the ecosystem and Level 5 is the highest, and it establishes the complete saturation of it as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Local Ecosystem Readiness Level classification

LERL	Description of presence and appropriateness of actors, services, infrastructures, and expertise.
1	Absence
2	Emergency
3	Development
4	Diffusion
5	Saturation

Source: Sarri et al., 2020

This assessment helps stakeholders understand where the ecosystem stands in terms of its networking and collaboration capabilities, identify areas for improvement, and determine appropriate strategies and interventions to advance the ecosystem toward higher levels of maturity.

The Playbook and Toolbox will serve as valuable resources, offering guidance and support to improve various aspects of the ecosystem depending on their maturity level, as reflected earlier in Figure 3. These tools facilitate a structured approach to address areas of improvement and advance the ecosystem's journey towards becoming an ERA Hub.

Subsequently, the indicators and their associated maturity levels can be used to place an ecosystem into a specific “phase” in the process of becoming an ERA Hub. Figure 5 showcases an initial version of the ERA Hub accreditation process.

Figure 5: Phase of ERA Hub development

Source: Consortium partners

2.4 Labelling or scoring system to measure the degree of maturity of ecosystems

The degree of maturity of ecosystems can be acknowledged through different systems: through a scoring system, through a labelling system or through awards. These are intended to 1) incentivize progress within the ecosystems; and to 2) identify best practices and inspiration models.

- First, different scorings for categories could be a valuable option when assessing the maturity of an ecosystem. In the context of such a scoring system, it may be beneficial to translate the phases or maturity levels into Ecosystem Readiness Levels (ERL), similar to a technology readiness level (TRL) system. It is important to determine the expected performance of ecosystems across the dimensions being assessed, as it may not be necessary to achieve a perfect score in all categories to progress to a particular phase, maturity level, or ERL. However, there is no universal model that fits all ecosystems, which calls for customization. For instance, the creation of diverse scenarios based on performance across categories of lines of action would allow for a comparison between ecosystems and enable the assessment of their maturity levels.
- Second, the introduction of a label would be interesting from the perspective of giving visibility to excellent ecosystems that can inspire others in their path towards becoming an ERA Hub. This type of approach would, however, require regular maintenance (e.g., on a yearly basis), as the concept of an ecosystem's "golden standard" evolves over time, as do the scoring criteria for affiliated ecosystems.
- Third, another option would be the use of awards to recognize progress made in an ecosystem during a given year. This approach could be more inclusive for ecosystems at lower maturity levels and could shift the project's focus towards the ambition of ecosystem improvement rather than solely measurable outcomes. This option underscores the significance of exploring different outlooks during the collaborative process of co-creating the framework.

3 Compliance criteria

Compliance criteria are considered in terms of their overall alignment with the above framework. The lines of action identified for ERA Hubs are utilised as a basis for the compliance criteria, as outlined in the Playbook. The following chapter, presents the compliance criteria as a function of the lines of action as follows:

- Research
- Talent
- Knowledge transfer
- Funding
- Collaboration
- Governance
- Innovation

3.1 Research

For the line of action related to research, the following compliance criteria are outlined related to the hallmarks of strong research performance (see **Error! Reference source not found.** below).

Table 1 Compliance criteria related to the research line of action for a future ERA Hub

Hallmarks of strong research performance	Compliance criteria
Citation index and publication output	Maintain a citation index and publication output that meets or exceeds the average for reputable academic and research communities in the same disciplines.
Number of scientific employees	Maintain a ratio of scientific employees to the scale and complexity of research activities that is competitive within the academic and research community.
Number of large research centres	Ensure an optimal number of large research centres that align with the ecosystem’s strategic goals and do not compromise effective management and support.
Diversity of research areas	Maintain a diverse portfolio of research areas that align with the ecosystem’s mission and contribute to the advancement of knowledge.
Research and development investment	Align research and development investment with strategic goals, industry needs, and measurable research outcomes.

Source: Consortium partners

These compliance criteria, coupled with the recommended strategies, aim to establish a strong research ecosystem which can push the boundaries of existing knowledge, address societal needs, and drive economic growth. Regular assessments and adjustments will be crucial to ensuring ongoing success.

3.2 Talent

For the line of action related to talent, the following compliance criteria are outlined related to the hallmarks of strong talent development and retention (see **Error! Reference source not found.** below).

Table 2 Compliance criteria related to the talent line of action for a future ERA Hub

Hallmarks of strong talent development and retention	Recommendations for development
Employment figures	Maintain positive employment figures, reflected in low turnover rates and high employee satisfaction.
Industry sounding board/involvement of employers	Foster active industry collaboration by involving employers in advisory roles and ensuring their engagement in research activities.
Attraction of talent from outside the ecosystem	Attract talent globally, as evidenced by the recruitment of individuals with diverse backgrounds and experiences.
Liveability and attractive workplaces for international talent	Enhance the liveability and attractiveness of workplaces, especially for international talent, by providing support for relocation, language assistance, and cultural integration.

Source: Consortium partners

These compliance criteria, coupled with the recommended strategies, aim to establish a supportive environment for talent development and retention within the ecosystem. Regular assessments and adjustments will be crucial to ensuring ongoing success.

3.3 Knowledge transfer

For the line of action related to research, the following compliance criteria are outlined related to the hallmarks of strong knowledge transfer (see **Error! Reference source not found.** below).

Table 3 Compliance criteria related to the knowledge transfer line of action for a future ERA Hub

Hallmarks of strong knowledge transfer	Recommendations for development
Trust	Cultivate trust in knowledge transfer processes, ensuring transparent and reliable communication between stakeholders.
Low barriers to entry	Minimize barriers to entry for knowledge transfer, fostering an environment that encourages easy access to and dissemination of valuable information.
Key account management	Implement effective key account management strategies to facilitate the smooth transfer of knowledge and maintain strong relationships with key stakeholders.
Engaging formats	Deliver knowledge transfer in engaging formats that resonate with the target audience, promoting effective communication and understanding.

Source: Consortium partners

These compliance criteria, coupled with the recommended strategies, aim to establish a robust framework for knowledge transfer within the ecosystem. Regular assessments and adjustments will be crucial to ensuring ongoing effectiveness in knowledge dissemination and utilization.

3.4 Funding

For the line of action related to funding, the following compliance criteria are outlined related to the hallmarks of well-functioning funding (see **Error! Reference source not found.** below).

Table 4 Compliance criteria related to the funding line of action for a future ERA Hub

Hallmarks of well-functioning funding	Recommendations for development
Diversity and availability of funding	Ensure a diverse and readily available pool of funding sources to support the ecosystem's various projects and initiatives.
Combination of funding streams	Utilize a combination of funding streams to provide comprehensive financial support, leveraging various sources for sustained ecosystem development.
Transparency	Maintain transparency in the funding process, providing clear and accessible information on funding opportunities, criteria, and decision-making processes.
Feedback mechanisms	Establish feedback mechanisms to engage stakeholders in the funding process, allowing for input and continuous improvement.
Legitimacy	Ensure the legitimacy of funding decisions, aligning them with the strategic goals and mission of the ecosystem.

Source: Consortium partners

These compliance criteria, paired with the recommended strategies, aim to establish a well-functioning funding ecosystem that supports the diverse needs of projects and initiatives within the ecosystem. Regular assessments and adjustments will be essential to adapting to evolving funding landscapes and priorities.

3.5 Collaboration

For the line of action related to collaboration, the following compliance criteria are outlined related to the hallmarks of powerful collaboration (see **Error! Reference source not found.** below).

Table 5 Compliance criteria related to the collaboration line of action for a future ERA Hub

Hallmarks of powerful collaboration	Recommendations for development
Collaboration agreements	Establish clear and formal collaboration agreements that outline roles, responsibilities, and expectations for all involved parties.
Strategic partnerships	Form strategic partnerships that align with the goals and objectives of the collaborating entities, fostering mutually beneficial relationships.
Tangible Outcomes	Focus on achieving tangible outcomes from collaborations, such as joint projects, shared resources, and measurable impact.
Trust and openness	Cultivate a culture of trust and openness among collaborators, creating an environment conducive to effective communication and collaboration.

Source: Consortium partners

These compliance criteria, coupled with the recommended strategies, aim to establish a framework for powerful collaboration within the ecosystem. Regular assessments and adjustments will be crucial to ensuring ongoing effectiveness in fostering collaboration and achieving meaningful outcomes.

3.6 Governance

For the line of action related to research, the following compliance criteria are outlined related to the hallmarks of strong governance (see **Error! Reference source not found.** below).

Table 6 Compliance criteria related to the governance line of action for a future ERA Hub

Hallmarks of strong governance	Recommendations for development
Trust and transparency	Cultivate a culture of trust and transparency among collaborators, ensuring open communication and shared information.
Political support	Secure political support for collaborative initiatives, involving key stakeholders and ensuring alignment with broader political goals.
Public discourse and open discussion	Promote public discourse and open discussion on collaborative projects, fostering inclusivity and diverse perspectives.
Clear definition of roles and responsibilities	Establish a clear and formalized definition of roles and responsibilities for all collaborators, minimizing ambiguity and promoting accountability.
Frequent review of strategy and impact with control mechanisms	Implement frequent reviews of collaborative strategy and impact, incorporating control mechanisms to assess progress and adjust strategies as needed.

Source: Consortium partners

These compliance criteria, paired with the recommended strategies, aim to establish a powerful collaboration framework within the ecosystem. Regular assessments and adjustments will be essential to ensure ongoing success in fostering collaborative initiatives and achieving meaningful impact.

3.7 Innovation

For the line of action related to innovation, the following compliance criteria are outlined related to the hallmarks of a strong innovation ecosystem (see **Error! Reference source not found.** below).

Table 7 Compliance criteria related to the innovation line of action for a future ERA Hub

Hallmarks of a strong innovation ecosystem	Recommendations for development
Patents	Increase the number of patents filed and granted, showcasing a robust innovation output.
Licensing agreements	Facilitate and increase licensing agreements, indicating successful commercialization and utilization of intellectual property.
Number of start-ups	Foster the creation and growth of startups within the ecosystem, demonstrating a vibrant entrepreneurial environment.
Funding	Ensure a steady and diverse flow of funding sources to support innovation initiatives and projects.
Mentorships	Establish mentorship programs to support entrepreneurs and innovators, contributing to their professional development.
Availability of education	Embed innovation in university education across study programs, fostering a culture of creativity and problem-solving.
Talent pool	Adopt a place-based approach and prioritise sustainability

	Develop and enhance infrastructure to support innovation activities, ensuring the availability of resources to nurture a skilled talent pool.
--	---

Source: Consortium partners

These compliance criteria, aligned with the recommended strategies, aim to contribute to the development of a strong and sustainable innovation ecosystem. Regular assessments and adjustments will be crucial to adapting to evolving innovation trends and priorities.

4 Guidelines & recommendations

Building upon the above indicated compliance criteria, it is possible to delineate, likewise working from the Playbook, a set of guidelines to assess the compliance criteria to understand an ecosystem’s fit with the ERA hubs model as presently proposed. Along the lines of the compliance criteria, also the guidelines are drafted using the lines of action as a point of departure.

4.1 Research

Guidelines for ecosystem to achieve the above outlined research compliance criteria include taking steps to:

- Enhance research capacity and capabilities within key disciplines through continuous investment in cutting-edge infrastructure, including laboratories, computational resources, and access to relevant databases and literature.
- Promote research ethics and integrity through the implementation of regular training programs for scientific employees, emphasizing responsible conduct in research and ethical considerations.
- Encourage open science practices by establishing mechanisms for collaboration and information-sharing among research centers. Foster an environment that values transparency and openness in the research process.
- Support long-term research projects and initiatives by allocating resources to interdisciplinary collaborations and providing incentives for researchers to explore emerging and underrepresented fields.
- Promote a culture of research entrepreneurship and commercialization by facilitating partnerships with industry, supporting technology transfer initiatives, and providing resources for researchers to translate their findings into tangible applications and solutions.

Recommendation for ecosystems aiming to improve and strengthen their research efforts as part of the journey to become an ERA Hub are:

- Enhance research capacity and capabilities within key disciplines through infrastructure
- Promote research ethics and integrity
- Encourage open science practices

- Support long-term research projects and initiatives
- Promote a culture of research entrepreneurship and commercialization
- Develop research-focused policies and strategies

Establishing Centres of Excellence is the tool that can be employed by an ecosystem towards the implementation of the ERA Hub framework mode.

4.2 Talent

Guidelines for ecosystem to achieve the above outlined talent compliance criteria include taking steps to:

- Implement talent attraction and retention strategies, ensuring competitive compensation, benefits, and a positive work environment. Regularly monitor and assess employee satisfaction and turnover rates.
- Establish skills development programs to enhance the capabilities of employees, promoting continuous learning and professional development. Encourage employees to stay updated on industry trends and acquire new skills.
- Promote diversity and inclusion initiatives to create an inclusive environment that values and celebrates diverse perspectives.
- Foster international collaborations by engaging in joint research projects, international conferences, and partnerships with global institutions. Enhance internationalization efforts by providing comprehensive support for international researchers, including assistance with relocation, language support, and cultural integration.

Recommendation for ecosystems aiming to improve and strengthen their talent development efforts as part of the journey to become an ERA Hub are:

- Implement talent attraction and retention strategies
- Establish skills development programmes
- Promote diversity and inclusion initiatives
- Foster international collaborations
- Enhance internationalisation efforts
- Emphasise continuous learning and professional development

Diversity outreach programmes and Thematic challenges are the tools that can be employed by an ecosystem towards the implementation of the ERA Hub framework mode.

4.3 Knowledge transfer

Guidelines for ecosystem to achieve the above outlined knowledge transfer compliance criteria include taking steps to:

- Foster a culture of continuous learning and collaboration, encouraging researchers and innovators to actively share and exchange knowledge within the ecosystem. Also promote

international collaboration and knowledge exchange by actively participating in global initiatives, partnerships, and collaborative projects.

- Provide training and capacity-building programs for researchers and innovators, enhancing their skills in effective communication and knowledge transfer. Also implement effective communication and outreach strategies to disseminate knowledge to a wider audience, utilizing various formats such as workshops, webinars, and interactive sessions.
- Strengthen partnerships with industry, government, and non-profit organizations to create collaborative platforms for knowledge exchange.
- Cultivate an entrepreneurial ecosystem for commercialization, facilitating the transfer of knowledge from research to practical applications in the market.

Recommendation for ecosystems to improve and strengthen their knowledge transfer capabilities are:

- Foster a culture of continuous learning and collaboration
- Provide training and capacity building programmes for researchers and innovators
- Strengthen partnerships with industry, government, and non-profit organisations
- Implement effective communication and outreach strategies
- Cultivate an entrepreneurial ecosystem for commercialisation
- Promote international collaboration and knowledge exchange
- Develop robust infrastructure for efficient knowledge transfer

Mentorship programmes and Popular science events are the tools that can be employed by an ecosystem towards the implementation of the ERA Hub framework mode.

4.4 Funding

Guidelines for ecosystem to achieve the above outlined funding compliance criteria include taking steps to:

- Build relationships with investors and venture capitalists for additional funding, fostering a network of financial support for diverse projects. Also implement robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for informed funding decisions, ensuring accountability and demonstrating the impact of funded projects.
- Develop a strategic plan for funding allocation and prioritization, aligning financial resources with the ecosystem's overarching goals and priorities. Also encourage risk willingness and support for start-ups, creating an environment that fosters innovation and entrepreneurship.
- Provide training and assistance in grant writing and proposal development to enhance the competitiveness of funding applications. Also explore opportunities for funding projects with social or environmental impact, attracting support from impact-focused investors and organizations.
- Encourage a public-private mix in funding, fostering collaboration between public institutions, private enterprises, and government bodies. Also establish partnership funds and corporate sponsorship programs to diversify funding sources and encourage collaboration with the private sector.

Recommendation that can help a research and innovation ecosystem establish a robust and diversified funding structure are:

- Build relationships with investors and venture capitalists for additional funding
- Develop a strategic plan for funding allocation and prioritisation-
- Provide training and assistance in grant writing and proposal development
- Explore opportunities for funding projects with social or environmental impact
- Implement robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for informed funding decisions
- Encourage a public-private mix in funding
- Establish partnership funds and corporate sponsorship programmes
- Encourage risk willingness and support for start-ups
- Enable cascade funding
- Support early-career researchers

Grants & soft funding is the tool that can be employed by an ecosystem towards the implementation of the ERA Hub framework mode.

4.5 Collaboration

Guidelines for ecosystem to achieve the above outlined collaboration compliance criteria include taking steps to:

- Promote networking and relationship-building, facilitating interactions among individuals and organizations to identify potential collaboration opportunities. Also facilitate communication and information-sharing through the use of platforms, tools, and events that encourage the exchange of ideas and knowledge.
- Provide infrastructure and technological support to enable seamless collaboration, including shared workspaces, collaborative tools, and access to relevant technologies.
- Foster internationalization and cross-border collaboration by actively seeking partnerships with entities outside the immediate ecosystem, expanding collaboration opportunities globally. Also build trust and enhance collaboration initiatives through initiatives that promote transparency, open communication, and a shared commitment to common goals.

Recommendation to establish various activities and mechanisms that promote collaboration, such as networking, communication, infrastructure support, and internationalization are:

- Promote networking and relationship-building
- Facilitate communication and information sharing
- Provide infrastructure and technological support
- Foster internationalisation and cross-border collaboration
- Build trust and enhance collaboration initiatives

MiniSprint and Industry involvement in courses are the tools that can be employed by an ecosystem towards the implementation of the ERA Hub framework mode.

4.6 Governance

Guidelines for ecosystem to achieve the above outlined governance compliance criteria include taking steps to:

- Enhance mechanisms for stakeholder engagement, involving diverse stakeholders in collaborative processes and decision-making.
- Establish a conducive governance framework that supports effective collaboration, defining roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes. Also develop a robust policy and strategic framework to guide collaborative initiatives, ensuring alignment with overarching goals and objectives.
- Foster internationalization and cross-border collaboration by actively seeking partnerships beyond local boundaries. Also invest in capacity-building programs to enhance the skills and capabilities of collaborators, promoting a more effective and resilient collaborative environment.
- Implement effective monitoring methods and conflict resolution mechanisms to address challenges and conflicts that may arise during collaboration. Also enhance transparency and accountability by adopting practices that promote openness, information sharing, and clear reporting on collaborative activities.

Recommendation to establish an ecosystem that can foster trust, a clear vision and mission, open dialogue, a conducive legal and regulatory framework, capacity building programmes, and international cooperation are:

- Enhance mechanisms for stakeholder engagement
- Establish a conducive governance framework
- Develop a robust policy and strategic framework
- Foster internationalisation and cross-border collaboration
- Invest in capacity building programmes
- Implement effective monitoring methods and conflict resolution mechanisms
- Enhance transparency and accountability

Stakeholder engagement and collaboration platforms are the tools that can be employed by an ecosystem towards the implementation of the ERA Hub framework mode.

4.7 Innovation

Guidelines for ecosystem to achieve the above outlined innovation compliance criteria include taking steps to:

- Facilitate stronger industry engagement, encouraging collaboration between academia and industry to address real-world challenges and enhance ecosystem connectivity for knowledge exchange, creating platforms for researchers, entrepreneurs, and industry professionals to share insights and expertise.
- Establish effective pathways for research commercialization, ensuring that innovations and research outcomes can be successfully brought to market.

- Expand global partnerships and collaborations, fostering international connections that contribute to a diverse and dynamic innovation ecosystem and foster diversity, networks, and a bottom-up approach, encouraging inclusivity and diverse perspectives to drive innovation from various sources within the community.
- Adopt a place-based approach and prioritize sustainability, tailoring innovation strategies to the specific characteristics and needs of the local ecosystem.

Recommendation for an ecosystem to improve its innovation capabilities, areas such as infrastructure development, industry engagement, knowledge sharing, research commercialisation, global partnerships, and sustainability are:

- Embed innovation in university education across study programmes
- Develop and enhance infrastructure to support innovation activities
- Facilitate stronger industry engagement
- Enhance ecosystem connectivity for knowledge exchange
- Establish effective pathways for research commercialisation
- Expand global partnerships and collaborations
- Adopt a place-based approach and prioritise sustainability
- Foster diversity, networks, and a bottom-up approach

Start-up programmes and Start-up Boot Camp are the tools that can be employed by an ecosystem towards the implementation of the ERA Hub framework mode.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, the document titled "D3.1 – Platform & Compliance Criteria - Release I" serves as a comprehensive guide that delineates the core aspects of the COOPERATE project for the integration of the Toolbox and Playbook developed within Work Package 2. Executed within Work Package 3, Task 3.1, led by IDEA Consult, the primary objective of the report is to develop the platform and compliance criteria crucial for establishing and advancing the ERA Hubs network. The overarching aim is to attract and connect stakeholders within EU ecosystems, including policy makers and society at large, while facilitating the use of the Toolbox and Playbook through online digital tools.

The report initiates with a contextual overview of the COOPERATE project and the ERA Hub framework, presented as a 4D matrix comprising Mission, Thematic scope, Lines of action, and Actors involved. It also provides a summary of diverse approaches for measuring and assessing ecosystem maturity levels, a pivotal factor in evaluating progress toward becoming ERA Hubs.

Aligned with the established framework, the report introduces compliance criteria, grounded in the identified Lines of action for ERA Hubs, as detailed in the Playbook. Lastly, the document outlines a set of guidelines to evaluate compliance criteria, gauging how well an ecosystem aligns with the proposed ERA hubs model. These guidelines, mirroring the compliance criteria, are formulated based on the identified lines of action.

In the ongoing evolution of the project, we anticipate additional insights and refinements to emerge from the Playbook, Toolbox, Co-creation Sessions, and the ongoing pilot implementation of the ERA

Hub model. These valuable learnings and refinements will be thoughtfully incorporated into the forthcoming updated version of this report, with an expected completion date by month 27 (M27).

To further enrich this process, a workshop will be organised. The goal is to convene stakeholders from diverse backgrounds and geographical locations across the European Union. The primary objective of this workshop is to facilitate in-depth discussions and collaborative efforts aimed at defining and fine-tuning crucial aspects of the platform. Specifically, the focus will be on delineating the platform's added value, specifying its array of services, and crafting a user journey that resonates with the dynamic needs of ecosystem on their path to becoming an ERA Hub. This inclusive approach guarantees that the platform's development is not an isolated endeavour but a collective and adaptive process, resonating with the diverse perspectives and evolving needs of stakeholders across the European Union. This will ensure that the platform aligns with the evolving needs of ecosystems on their journey to becoming an ERA Hub.

6 Bibliography

European Commission (2017). Strengthening Innovation in Europe's Regions: Strategies for resilient, inclusive and sustainable growth. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions

Roger, S., Spaapen, J., Bauer, M.W., Hogan, E., Revuelta, G. and Stagl, S., (2015). Indicators for promoting and monitoring responsible research and innovation: report from the expert group on policy indicators for responsible research and innovation.

Russell, Martha G., and Nataliya V. Smorodinskaya (2018). Leveraging complexity for ecosystemic innovation. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 136, 114-131.

Sarri, D., Lombardo, S., Pagliai, A., Perna, C., Lisci, R., De Pascale, V., Rimediotti, M., Cencini, G., Vieri, M. (2020). Smart Farming Introduction in Wine Farms: A Systematic Review and a New Proposal. *Sustainability*, 12(17): 7191.